

Assessment of Seasonal Variations in Water Quality of Pampa River with Special Emphasis on Pilgrim Season

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Abstract- The Pampa River, one of Kerala's prominent rivers, plays a vital ecological, cultural, and religious role, serving as the lifeline of the Sabarimala pilgrimage. Every year, during the Mandala-Makaravilakku season, a large influx of pilgrims leads to a significant increase in waste generation, sewage inflow, and ritual-based discharges into the river. In addition to these anthropogenic influences, natural factors such as monsoon floods, pre-monsoon low flows, and seasonal fluctuations further affect the river's water quality. This study undertakes a systematic, seasonal, and event-based assessment of the Pampa River to understand pollution dynamics, identify critical stress periods, and support sustainable river basin management and pilgrimage planning. During the pilgrimage season, the river is extensively used by devotees for bathing and various ritual activities, often resulting in contamination and a decline in water quality. The present work involves water quality evaluation during three phases before, during, and after the pilgrimage season using the Water Quality Index (WQI) method integrated with GIS-based spatial analysis. The study examines physical, chemical, and microbiological parameters, including oxygen demand, nutrient concentrations, and indicators of organic and inorganic pollutants, along with other relevant water quality determinants from September to February month. The results clearly indicate that the river water quality is highly dynamic and is significantly influenced by both natural seasonal variations and anthropogenic activities.

Keywords: Pampa river, parameters, Oxygen demand, Nutrients, microbiological parameters, organic and inorganic pollutants indicators, GIS, Water quality index.

I.INTRODUCTION

The Pampa River in Kerala, India, is one of the state's most significant and revered perennial water bodies. The Pilgrim Season (typically from November to February) witnesses an enormous influx of an estimated 40-50 million devotees annually. The town of Pamba, situated near the temple, serves as a vital base camp for the pilgrimage. Devotees traditionally use the river for ritualistic bathing, washing clothes, and other sanitary purposes. This massive, temporary concentration of people, coupled with inadequate infrastructure for waste management, sanitation, and sewage treatment, introduces an overwhelming load of anthropogenic pollution into the river. Key pollution sources during this period include: Microbiological contamination that is high concentrations of faecal coliforms and E. coli from human waste, often soaring to levels far

exceeding permissible limits, making the water unfit for bathing and drinking, Nutrient loading such as discharge of detergents, soap, and food waste increases the levels of phosphorus and nitrogen, which can lead to eutrophication, Solid Waste that includes, Indiscriminate dumping of plastic, cloth, and other biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste directly into the river also degrade the water quality along with the aesthetic appearance.

The study conjectures, local relevance of Pampa River that is ecologically and culturally important in Kerala, especially due to Sabarimala pilgrimage and seasonal variation such as Pre-monsoon, monsoon, post-monsoon, and pilgrimage season water quality can be compared to highlight anthropogenic impacts.

1.1 Objectives

- To analyse the physio-chemical and microbiological characteristics of Pampa River water across different seasons, from September to February.
- To evaluate the impact of pilgrim season on the water quality compared to non-pilgrim periods.
- To compute the Water Quality Index (WQI) for different sites and seasons.
- To identify pollution hotspots and major contributing factors.
- To propose management strategies for improving water quality during high-stress periods.

1.2 Scope of this study

- Supports river conservation and management policies.
- Findings can aid Kerala State Pollution Control Board and local authorities.
- Can be extended to GIS mapping of pollution hotspots or climate influence on river water quality.

II. METHODOLOGY

The present study focuses on evaluating the physico-chemical, biological, and microbiological characteristics of river water across different locations and seasons. The study was carried out at selected sampling locations along the Pampa River, including upstream, midstream, and downstream regions, representing varying degrees of anthropogenic influence.

Fig 2.1 Methodology Flow chart

2.1 Study Area

The Pampa River Basin is one of the important river basins in Kerala, India, originating from the Ponniamkuthu hills of the Western Ghats at about 1650 m elevation.

1.Upstream of Pampa River (L1). This site is selected as a control station to represent natural background water quality and also for understanding the depth of pollution at downstream locations.

2. Pampa Bathing Ghats (L2). This point is selected to analyse the direct impact of mass pilgrimage activities.

3. Ranni-Perunad(L3). It is a transitional zone where the river begins to experience both the natural flow and human influences.

4.Aranmula (L4). Where both pilgrim activities and other human activities involved. The self-purification capacity in downstream is detracted due to both cultural and human activities.

5.Chengannur(L5). his site represents the cumulative impact zone where all pollutants accumulate and making it critical for assessing overall river health before confluence.

2.2 Method of Analysis

The parameters that belong to respective physical, chemical, microbiological, metals and other related parameter are analyzed with their respective method, depicted in below table.

SLNO	PARAMETER	METHOD OF ANALYSIS	ACCEPTED VALUE
1	pH	pH meter	6.5 – 8.5
2	Turbidity (NTU)	Turbidity tube	1 – 5 NTU
3	Colour (CU)	Comparator	5 – 15 CU
4	Odour	sensory	Acceptable
5	Temperature (°C)	Thermometer	—
6	Total Hardness (as CaCO ₃)	EDTA titration	≤ 200 mg/L (acc.), 600 mg/L (max)
7	Calcium Hardness	EDTA titration	≤ 75 mg/L
8	Magnesium Hardness	Calculation, by difference	≤ 30 mg/L
9	Alkalinity (Total)	Acid titration	≤ 200 mg/L
10	Chloride (as Cl ⁻)	Argentometric	≤ 250 mg/L
11	Fluoride (as F ⁻)	SPADNS method	0.6 – 1.5 mg/L
12	Nitrate (as NO ₃ ⁻)	Colorimetric	≤ 45 mg/L
13	Nitrite (as NO ₂ ⁻)	Colorimetric	≤ 0.3 mg/L
14	Ammonia (as NH ₃ -N)	Nessler method	≤ 0.5 mg/L
15	Iron (as Fe)	Phenanthroline	≤ 0.3 mg/L
16	Manganese (as Mn)	Colorimetric	≤ 0.1 mg/L
17	Sulphate (as SO ₄ ²⁻)	Turbidimetric	≤ 200 mg/L
18	Phosphate (as PO ₄ ³⁻)	Colorimetric	≤ 0.3 mg/L
19	Residual Chlorine	DPD method	0.2 – 0.5 mg/L
20	Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	Winkler method	≥ 4 mg/L
21	Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)	BOD ₅ method	< 5mg/l
22	Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)	Dichromate method	≤ 250 mg/L
23	Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	Gravimetric / meter	≤ 500 mg/L (acc.), 2000 mg/L (max)
24	Electrical Conductivity (EC)	Conductivity meter	< 300µs/cm
25	Total Coliforms	Presence-absence vial	0 MPN/100 mL
26	Faecal Coliforms (E. coli)	Presence-absence vial	0 MPN/100 mL

Table 2.1 Method of analysis

2.3 Water Quality Index

A water quality index is mathematical tool that simplifies complex data from multiple physical, chemical and biological water parameters into a single numerical value. A water quality index is a single, dimensionless, numerical score often ranges from 0-100 that translates complex. It assess physical, chemical and biological factors such as dissolved Oxygen, PH, BOD and fecal coliform to determine if water is safe for uses like drinking or recreational purposes.

Water quality index Calculation

Calculate quality rating, Q_i

$$Q_i = \frac{(v_i - v_0)}{(s_i - v_0)} \times 100$$

v_i = observed value

$$v_0 = \text{Ideal value of that parameter in pure water}$$

$$s_i = \text{Standard Permissible value}$$

Standard Permissible value

Formula for Unit Weight (W_i)

$$W_i = K/S_i$$

Common V_o values, where: pH-7, DO-14.6, All other parameters 0

K= proportionality constant

$$k = 1/\sum(1/S_i) = 1/0.9961$$

$$K \approx 1.0039$$

S_i=Standard Permissible value

Calculate unit weights (W_i)

$$W_i = K/S_i$$

Final WQI Equation,

$$WQI = \sum(Q_i W_i) / \sum W_i$$

Since,

$$\sum W_i = 1$$

$$WQI = \sum(Q_i W_i)$$

WQI RANGE	WATER QUALITY
0-25	Excellent
26-50	Good
51-75	Poor
76-100	Very Poor
>100	unsuitable

Table 2.2 WQI Classification Table

2.4 GIS Software

QGIS-Quantum Geographic Information System-is a free, open -source geographic information system (GIS). The GIS-based analysis of Water Quality Index (WQI) was carried out using QGIS software by following a systematic methodology. Initially, the geographical coordinates (latitude and longitude) of all sampling locations (L1–L5) were collected during field sampling. These spatial coordinates, along with the corresponding WQI values for each month (September to February), were organized in a spreadsheet format and saved as a CSV file. The prepared dataset was then imported into QGIS as a delimited text layer, where each sampling point was accurately plotted on the map based on its geographic coordinates. A suitable base map, such as OpenStreetMap, was added to provide spatial reference and context to the study area. The attribute table was verified to ensure correct linking of WQI values with their respective locations. Subsequently, the point

data was symbolized using a categorized color scheme based on WQI classification ranges (e.g., Good, Poor, Very Poor and Unsuitable) to visually represent water quality conditions at each location.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From September to February, the 26 Parameters is analysed over 5 locations by taking three water samples from each locations.

- The September water quality assessment across five locations (L1 to L5) indicates a gradual deterioration of water quality from upstream (L1) to downstream (L5), influenced mainly by increased anthropogenic activities, organic load, and ionic concentration. Microbiological Quality, Total coliforms and fecal coliforms showed a drastic increase from 60–65 MPN/100 mL (L1) to 2500–2800 MPN/100 mL (L5). This clearly indicates severe faecal contamination and makes downstream water unsafe for direct domestic use without treatment. The September analysis reveals that water quality degradation is progressive and location dependent, with downstream sites significantly impacted by sewage discharge, surface runoff, and human activities.
- The October water quality assessment indicates a distinct post-monsoon transition phase, where the river system shifts from dilution-dominated conditions to increasing anthropogenic influence. Overall, water quality shows gradual deterioration from Location 1 to Location 5, reflecting cumulative pollutant loading downstream. Dissolved Oxygen (DO) levels were satisfactory (>6 mg/L) at upstream sites, but declined downstream, with BOD and COD increasing sharply, especially at Locations 4 and 5. water quality reflects moderate pollution stress, with upstream segments maintaining good ecological condition, while downstream stretches exhibit organic, nutrient, and microbial pollution due to cumulative anthropogenic impact. Seasonal recession of monsoon

flows reduces dilution, making pollution effects more pronounced.

Sl. No	PARAMETER	NOVEMBER														
		Location 1			Location 2			Location 3			Location 4			Location 5		
		S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3
1	pH	6.5	6.8	6.6	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.4	6.3	6.4	6.4	6.8	6.6	6.7	6.8
2	Turbidity (NTU)	2.1	2.2	2.0	20	32	35	14	16	17	14	16	18	19	19	21
3	Coliform (CFU)	4	4	5	33	32	33	26	28	28	24	22	24	32	31	33
4	DO (mg/L)	very fishable			high			moderate			moderate			moderate		
5	Temperature (°C)	24	24	24	29	28	28	26	27	26	27	26	27	26	27	28
6	Total Hardness (in CaCO ₃)	88	89	88	88	85	90	85	90	95	100	125	125	130	125	125
7	Calcium Hardness	35	36	38	46	48	48	56	56	57	55	53	54	60	65	62
8	Magnesium Hardness	18	18	19	20	28	29	30	29	28	26	28	28	24	30	32
9	Chloride (Cl ⁻)	88	90	88	128	132	140	90	95	98	120	130	134	135	140	142
10	Sulfate (SO ₄ ²⁻)	17	18	19	43	70	77	46	49	48	59	59	59	71	72	74
11	Hardness (in Ca ⁺⁺)	6.6	6.3	6.8	6.6	6.8	6.8	6.8	6.8	6.7	6.4	6.6	6.6	6.4	6.6	6.9
12	Hardness (in Mg ⁺⁺)	6.6	1.1	0.8	1.5	2.6	3.5	0.26	0.28	0.30	1.2	2.4	2.5	2.3	2.8	3.2
13	Salinity (in ppt)	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.16	0.17	0.20	0.07	0.08	0.11	0.04	0.12	0.06	0.7	0.6	0.6
14	Iron (in mg/L)	0.05	0.10	0.20	0.7	0.9	1.0	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.25	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.4	0.7

Sl. No	PARAMETER	NOVEMBER														
		S.1			S.2			S.3			S.4			S.5		
		S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3	S1	S2	S3
15	BOD (in mg/L)	0.10	0.14	0.17	0.27	0.33	0.35	0.27	0.33	0.34	0.42	0.53	0.48	0.49	0.59	0.66
16	Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)	0.63	0.63	0.67	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.65	0.66	0.66	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.93	0.93	0.94
17	Free Chlorine (in mg/L)	0	4	2	6	6	5	9	10	10	11	12	12	17	17	18
18	Free Chlorine (in % Cl ₂)	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.9	1.2	1.0	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.7
19	Residual Chlorine (in % Cl ₂)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.08	0.15	0.15	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.10	0.07	0.10	0.07	0.10	0.10
20	Residual Chlorine (in mg/L)	7.4	7.6	7.8	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.4
21	Phosphate (in mg/L)	5.8	5.8	6.1	1.6	2.2	2.0	2.2	2.0	2.1	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.0	4.0	4.0
22	Ammonia Nitrogen (in mg/L)	1.6	1.7	1.7	0.8	0.3	0.4	3	2.6	2.7	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
23	DO (mg/L)	6.2	6.1	6.1	5.1	5.4	5.6	5.0	5.1	5.0	5.1	5.1	5.1	5.1	5.1	5.1
24	Total Hardness (in mg/L)	70	80	90	140	170	200	120	140	150	120	130	140	160	160	160
25	Calcium Hardness (in mg/L)	30	30	30	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
26	Fecal Coliforms (in MPN/100 mL)	70	80	80	2000	2000	2000	1500	800	800	1000	900	900	2500	2500	2500

Table 3.1 November month Water analysis data table

- The November water quality data clearly demonstrate that peak pilgrimage season significantly degrades river water quality, primarily through organic loading, nutrient enrichment, and microbial contamination. Although most parameters remain within marginal permissible limits, the biological and bacteriological quality is severely compromised, making the water unsafe for direct human use without treatment. Increased Pilgrimage Activities Ritual bathing, washing, offerings, and food preparation near the river lead to Increased organic load (BOD, COD) Elevated nutrients (nitrate, phosphate, ammonia) High coliform and faecal coliform counts direct discharge of waste and inadequate sanitation facilities during peak crowd periods contribute to microbial contamination.
- The December water quality analysis of Pamba River during peak pilgrimage season indicates moderate to high pollution stress characterized by increased turbidity, nutrient enrichment, elevated BOD and

COD, reduced dissolved oxygen, and severe faecal contamination, especially in downstream pilgrimage-intensive locations. water quality clearly shows progressive deterioration from upstream to downstream locations, primarily due to intensified pilgrimage activities. While physico chemical parameters remain within marginally acceptable limits, organic pollution and bacteriological contamination are significantly elevated. The river's natural self-purification capacity is stressed due to reduced dilution (post-monsoon lower flow) and Increased pollutant load enhanced microbial activity at moderate temperatures.

- Overall, January water quality shows that upstream regions remain relatively clean, whereas downstream stretches are moderately to highly polluted due to domestic wastewater discharge, agricultural runoff, and human activities. Immediate pollution control measures and improved wastewater management are recommended to prevent further deterioration.
- February represents a post-pilgrimage and pre-summer transition period, where the river system enters a low-flow regime due to the absence of monsoonal recharge and a further reduction in discharge. February water quality can be characterized as a concentration-dominated system, where reduced dilution, accumulated pollutants, and ongoing low-level anthropogenic inputs contribute to moderate to high pollution levels, particularly in downstream regions.

Fig 3.1 Correlation graph of BOD vs COD and DO vs Temperature

3.2 Water Quality Index (WQI) Calculation

Monthly water quality index variation from September month to February month

Fig 3.2 Graphical representation of monthly water quality index Variation

Fig 3.3 Water quality curve

According to the water quality index for the respective months analysis it is concluded to classification of months regarding six different phases.

- September-Disturbance phase
- October-dilution and stabilization phase
- November-pilgrim impact phase
- December-peak impact phase
- January-Early recovery phase
- February-partial recovery phase

Fig 3.4 WQI distribution map of September and October month

3.3 WQI-Based Spatial Distribution Analysis Using GIS

Fig 3.6 WQI distribution map of January and February month

Fig 3.5 WQI distribution map of November and December month

IV.CONCLUSION

The present study provides a comprehensive evaluation of the water quality of the Pampa River through detailed analysis of physicochemical, chemical, biological, and microbiological parameters across multiple locations and seasons. The results clearly indicate that the river water quality is highly dynamic and is significantly influenced by both natural seasonal variations and anthropogenic activities.

A clear spatial variation in water quality was observed along the river course. The upstream region (L1), characterized by dense forest cover and minimal human interference, consistently exhibited good water quality with low turbidity, low nutrient concentration, high dissolved oxygen (DO), and minimal microbial contamination. This region represents the natural baseline condition of the river system.

In contrast, downstream locations (L4 and L5) showed significant deterioration in water quality due to cumulative impacts of domestic discharge, agricultural runoff, and urban activities. Key parameters such as turbidity, total dissolved solids (TDS), hardness, chloride,

nitrate, phosphate, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and chemical oxygen demand (COD) exhibited a progressive increase from upstream to downstream locations. Simultaneously, dissolved oxygen levels showed a decreasing trend, indicating higher organic pollution and oxygen stress in downstream stretches.

Seasonal variation played a crucial role in influencing water quality. During the monsoon and post-monsoon periods, increased surface runoff transported sediments, nutrients, and microbial contaminants into the river system. While dilution effects were observed in upstream regions, downstream areas experienced pollutant accumulation due to reduced self-purification capacity.

A major finding of this study is the significant impact of the Sabarimala pilgrimage season on river water quality. Elevated levels of total and fecal coliforms confirmed severe contamination, making the water unsuitable for direct use without treatment. The major hotspot is L2 (pampa bathing ghats), during the peak pilgrimage season the water is contaminated and the river is deteriorated in high.

4.1 Recommendations

The Pampa River is ecologically and culturally significant, supporting biodiversity as well as religious activities. Its protection requires a combination of engineering interventions, policy enforcement, and active public participation. The following recommendations are proposed to improve and sustain the water quality of the river:

- Improvement of sanitation infrastructure in pilgrimage zones
- Temporary bio toilets during pilgrimage
- Zonation for bathing activities
- Implementation of strict solid waste management systems:
- Regulation of pilgrimage activities and restriction of harmful practices
- Installation of decentralized wastewater treatment systems

- Promotion of riverbank protection and sustainable land use
- Establishment of continuous water quality monitoring systems
- Increase in public awareness and community participation
- Strengthening of regulatory enforcement and special monitoring staffs
- Use of GIS and modern tools for monitoring

REFERENCES

1. Bera, Subhankar. "The Interplay of Changing Environment and Water Management on the Degradation of Indian River Systems: Navigating Aspects of Fragility, Resiliency, and Sustainability." In *Reimagining Indian Rivers for Sustainability*, pp. 491-509. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2026.
2. Tiwari, Sushila, Rahul M. Jindal, and Dileep Mavalankar. "John Snow and the contaminated water of River Ganga at Kumbh Mela in India." *International Health* (2025): ihaf081.
3. Mishra, Mansi, Khushi Ahuja, and Rohit Rawat. "Assessment of Physicochemical, Heavy Metal, and Microbial Contamination in the Ganga River at Prayagraj Across Maha Kumbh Phases." (2025).
4. Kanaujiya, Ashok Kumar, and Vineet Tiwari. "Water quality analysis of River Ganga and Yamuna using water quality index (WQI) during Kumbh Mela 2019, Prayagraj, India." *Environment, Development and Sustainability* 26, no. 2 (2024): 5451-5472.
5. Rana, Vivek, Garima Dubish, Firoz Ahmad, and Ajit Kumar Vidyarthi. "Study of Water Quality of Ganga River and Its Suitability for Mass Ritualistic Bathing before Kumbh Mela-2021 at Haridwar in Uttarakhand, India." *Journal of Indian Water Works Association* (2022): 23-29.
6. Saha, Ajoy, Sibina Mol Salim, Deepa Sudheesan, Vettath Raghavan Suresh, Subir Kumar Nag, Preetha Panikkar, and Basanta Kumar Das. "Impacts of a Massive Flood Event on the Physico-Chemistry and Water Quality of River Pampa in Western Ghats of India." *International Journal of*

- Environmental Analytical Chemistry 102 (19): 7969–87. (2022)
doi:10.1080/03067319.2020.1843026.
7. Miserendino, María Laura, Cecilia Brand, Yanina Andrea Assef, Cristina Natalia Horak, Luz María Manzo, Luis Beltrán Epele, and Emilio Williams-Subiza. "Land-use effects on aquatic and wetland ecosystems: an overview of environmental impacts and tools for ecological assessment." *Freshwaters and Wetlands of Patagonia: Ecosystems and Socioecological Aspects* (2022): 295-321.
 8. Ramakrishnan, S., G. Anusha, K. Kirupasankar, C. Venkatesh, and S. Pradeep. "A Study on the Water Quality Assessment of Bhavani River in Tamil Nadu." In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1145, no. 1, p. 012068. IOP Publishing, 2021.
 9. Lekshmi, Subha, Athira Somarajan, Merlin Daniel, and Vishak Sasidhar. "Water Quality Analysis of River PAMBA using WQI Method and GIS Mapping." *international Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)* Published by: <http://www.ijert.org> ISSN: 2278-0181 Vol. 9 Issue 06, June-2020
 10. Rajeev, Rugma, and S. Manjary. "A Comparative Analysis of Microbiological Parameters of Pampa River and Achankovil River with Reference to Sabarimala Pilgrim Season." *Journal of Aquatic Biology & Fisheries* 109. (2020)
 11. Vidyarthi, Ajit Kumar, Vivek Rana, Garima Dublish, and Mrinal Kanti Biswas. "Water Quality of the River Ganga During Mass Ritualistic Bathing On Ardh Kumbh In Prayagraj, India." *Pollution Research* 39 (2020): S55-S58.
 12. George, Thomas., and Shaju K. John. "Water pollution and its impact rural health. Micro analysis based on River Pompa, Kerala, India." *Minor Research Project Report. University Grants Commission, South Block, Bangalore: 55pp* (2015).
 13. Nair, Sri NK Sukumaran, and Hariyana Hissar. "Biodiversity Conservation in Pampa River Basin."(2014)
 14. Tyagi, Shweta, Bhavtosh Sharma, Prashant Singh, and Rajendra Dobhal. "Water quality assessment in terms of water quality index." *American Journal of water resources* 1, no. 3 (2013): 34-38